

HYPOCHOLESTEROLEMIC EFFECT OF *NIGELLA SATIVA* AND *WITHANIA SOMNIFERA* IN LAYERS WITH REFERENCE TO HEPATIC AND OVARIAN FOLLICLE EXPRESSION OF CHOLESTEROL RELATED GENES

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Abstract

The regulation of cholesterol synthesis and uptake from plasma is dependent on coordinated changes in the level of mRNAs of key genes that are known to regulate cholesterol synthesis and cholesterol uptake. Sterol regulatory element binding proteins (SREBP)-1 and -2 are transcription factors for the LDLr gene and are critical molecules in the feedback system of cholesterol metabolism. In the present study, the effect of *Nigella Sativa* and *Withania Somnifera* on serum and egg cholesterol and expression of SREBP-2 and LDLr gene was determined in liver and ovarian follicles of layers. The experimental birds were fed one of four different diets supplemented with *Nigella Sativa* and *Withania Somnifera* for 84 days. Blood and egg samples were collected for determining cholesterol content and liver and ovarian follicles were collected for the gene expression analysis. Total RNA was isolated from the collected tissues following standard TRIzol method for first-strand cDNA synthesis. Expression of SREBP-2 and LDLr genes was quantified using gene specific primer pairs with Real-Time PCR. *Nigella Sativa* and *Withania Somnifera* alone and in combination, significantly decreased the serum and egg cholesterol and significantly increased the mRNA expression levels of Sterol Regulatory Element Binding Protein-2 (SREBP-2) and Low-Density Lipoprotein receptor (LDLr) gene in liver and ovarian follicles of layers indicating the hypocholesterolemic activity of these herbs.

Keywords: Hypocholesterolemic, LDLr, *Nigella sativa*, SREBP-2, *Withania Somnifera*

Introduction

Hypercholesterolemia is a key risk factor for the development and advancement of atherosclerosis and related cardiac disease. Epidemiological, clinical, genetic and experimental studies indicate that high serum level of low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C) is associated with the cause. Cholesterol is one of the main components of membrane lipids. Lipid homeostasis in vertebrate cells is controlled by sterol regulatory element-binding proteins (SREBPs). SREBPs activate the expression of over 30 genes directly which are involved in the synthesis and uptake of cholesterol, fatty acids, triglycerides and phospholipids. Sterol regulatory-element binding proteins (SREBPs) were recognized as a subclass of membrane-bound, basic helix-loop-helix leucine zipper (bHLH-LZ) transcription factors which control the promoters of genes involved in lipid synthesis and uptake pathways. Three major SREBP isoforms, SREBP-1a, -1c, and -2, have been identified and differ in relative abundance in the liver and other tissues. SREBP-1a is a powerful activator of all

SREBP-responsive genes and plays role to maintain basic levels of cholesterol and fatty acid. In contrast, SREBP-1c selectively activates genes involved in fatty acid synthesis, while SREBP-2 preferentially regulates genes important for cholesterol homeostasis. Low-density lipoprotein receptor (LDLr) is the primary receptor in liver for binding and internalization of plasma-derived LDL-cholesterol and has a major influence on plasma and intracellular cholesterol concentration. Sterol regulatory element binding proteins (SREBP)-1 and -2 are transcription factors for the LDLr gene and are critical molecules in the feedback system.

Several modern drugs in use such as statins, fibrates, nicotinic acid and resins, lower blood cholesterol level, either by inhibiting endogenous synthesis and/or by lowering cholesterol absorption from the intestine. The action of modern drugs is associated with side effects hence people are looking for safer replacements. Indigenous medicinal plants have been a major source of therapeutic agents since ancient times. The revival of interest in natural drugs started in last decade mainly because of the wide spread belief that green medicines are healthier than synthetic products.

Nigella Sativa seeds and oil extracted from it, are popular in various traditional systems of herbal medicine such as Ayurveda and Siddha as well as Unani and Tibb. These have been reported to have several biological activities including antioxidant, antimicrobial, antihypertensive, anticancer, anti-inflammatory, diuretics, anti-diarrheal, appetite stimulant, analgesics, and for treatment of skin disorders, therefore seeds of *N. sativa* can be considered as functional food components. Ashwagandha is a real potent regenerative tonic possessing several pharmacological properties like antioxidant, anxiolytic, adaptogen, memory enhancing, anti-parkinsonian, anti-inflammatory, antitumor properties etc. The present work was undertaken to determine the effect of *Nigella sativa* and *Withania somnifera* on serum and egg cholesterol and expression of SREBP-2 and LDLr gene in liver and ovarian follicles of layers.

Materials and Methods

The work was conducted in the Department of Veterinary Pharmacology and Toxicology, College of Veterinary Science and Animal Husbandry, Nanaji Deshmukh Veterinary Science University, Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh, India.

The study was conducted on a total of Forty-eight healthy Jabalpur colour birds of twenty-eight weeks age, after permission of Institutional Animal Ethics Committee. Birds were maintained and kept in individual cages under standard management conditions at All India Coordinated Research Project (A.I.C.R.P.) on poultry breeding farm, Adhartal, Jabalpur. All the experimental birds were kept under constant observations during the entire period (84 days) of study.

Seeds of *Nigella Sativa* and roots of *Withania Somnifera* (Ashwagandha) were obtained from the Department of Aromatic and Medicinal Plants, Agriculture College, Jawaharlal Nehru Krishi Vishwa Vidyalaya, Jabalpur. Roots of *Withania Somnifera* were dried, crushed, powdered and seeds of *Nigella Sativa* were used as such for supplementation of the diet in birds.

Four diets were formulated; one was control diet for group T₁ consisted of standard diet without any supplements. The rest of the diets consisted of standard diet along with 2 per cent *Nigella sativa* seeds for group T₂, 2 percent *Withania Somnifera* root powder for group T₃ and 1 percent *Nigella sativa* and 1 per cent *Withania Somnifera* for group T₄.

Birds were divided into four groups of 12 birds each. The details of experimental groups are mentioned in Table 01.

Table 01: Design of Experiment

Groups	No. of birds per treatment	Treatment	Sample collection
T ₁	12	Standard Diet	Blood, Egg, Liver and ovarian follicles were collected on day 84
T ₂	12	Standard Diet+ <i>Nigella sativa</i> (20 gm/kg feed)	Same as T ₁
T ₃	12	Standard Diet+ <i>Withaniasomnifera</i> (20 gm/kg feed)	Same as T ₁
T ₄	12	Standard Diet+ <i>Nigella sativa</i> (10 gm/kg feed) + <i>Withaniasomnifera</i> (10 gm/kg feed)	Same as T ₁

Blood and Egg Lipid Profile

Blood samples were collected from all experimental birds from wing vein in a sterile vial on day 84 of the experiment. Serum was separated and used for the estimation of serum cholesterol. Six eggs were collected from each dietary treatment group of birds on day 84 of the experiment. Yolk was collected from each egg for the extraction of lipids. Lipid was extracted from the egg yolk with chloroform: methanol mixture (2:1 v/v).

Quantitative estimation of cholesterol in serum and egg yolk was done by means of kit from Transasia Bio-Medicals Ltd., Mumbai in fully automated Biochemical analyzer (ERBA Mannheim-EM 200, Germany).

Differential Expression Analysis of SREBP-2 and LDLr Genes

For gene expression analysis the liver and ovarian follicle samples were collected aseptically from birds of both groups after the completion of the experiment. These birds were sacrificed following the appropriate standard procedure. Total RNA was isolated from the collected tissues following standard TRIzol method using TRIzol reagent (Sigma-aldrich, USA). The purity of RNA was checked before the preparation of first- strand cDNA. The first strand cDNA was synthesized using RevertAid™ first strand cDNA synthesis kit (Thermo Scientific, USA). Expression of SREBP-2 and LDLr genes was quantified using gene specific primer pairs using Real-Time PCR. Glyceraldehyde 3 phosphate dehydrogenase (GAPDH) was used as a reference gene.

Primers for Sterol Regulatory Element Binding Protein-2 (SREBP-2), Low Density Lipoprotein Receptor (LDLr) and Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase (GAPDH; used as housekeeping gene) were adopted. Sequence of gene specific primers for SREBP-2, LDLr and GAPDH were as follows:

S. No	Gene	Primer size	Product size	Primer sequence
1	SREBP-2 (F)	23	339	5'-ACAGACGCCAAGATGCACAAGTC-3'
2	SREBP-2 (R)	23		5'-CCACAGGAGGAGAGTCAGGTTCA-3'
3	LDLr (F)	21	108	5'-GGAGCAGTCACAGCATCAGCT-3'
4	LDLr (R)	22		5'-CTGTGTCACACTCCGCTGTCTC-3'
5	GAPDH (F)	23	543	5'-AAGCGTGTTATCATCTCAGCTCC-3'
6	GAPDH (R)	23		5'-CGCATCAAAGGTGGAGGAATGGC-3'

F= Forward, R= Reverse

Readymix Taq PCR Reaction mix with MgCl₂ (Sigma Aldrich, U.S.A.) was used to prepare PCR reaction mixture. The relative expression of gene specific mRNA was quantified by qRT-PCR/Real-time PCR employing SYBR green chemistry using Real-time PCR system (CFX Connect Real-time System, Bio-Rad laboratories Inc. USA).

Comparative C_T method was used for relative expression of target gene in the test sample (treatment) relative to that of control sample (calibrator). The relative expression of target genes was estimated in term of fold change in mRNA expression, using the following formula:

$$\text{Fold change in expression of target gene} = 2^{-\Delta\Delta C_T}$$

Statistical analysis of the data was done by using Hierarchical method and differences among the treatments and intervals were tested for significance by Duncan's Multiple Range Test.

Results

The efficacy of *Nigella sativa* and *Withania Somnifera* alone and in combination on serum and egg cholesterol in layers have been summarized in Table 2. Serum cholesterol was calculated in terms of mg/dl on day 84 of the experimental period in different treatment groups of birds. Untreated control (Group T₁) did not show any significant change in serum cholesterol and was 160.4±1.57 mg/dl on day 84 of the study. However, layers supplemented with indigenous herbs revealed significant (p<0.05) reduction in serum cholesterol on day 84 post treatment.

The concentration of cholesterol in egg yolk was calculated in terms of mg/gm of yolk on day 84 of the experimental period in different treatment groups of birds. The reduction in cholesterol concentration in egg was found significant (p<0.05) in all treatment groups except group T₁. The

reduction in egg yolk cholesterol concentration was found to be 8.94, 7.69 and 10.50 on day 84 post treatment in group T₂, T₃ and T₄ respectively.

Table 02: Efficacy of *Nigella Sativa* and *Withania Somnifera* on Serum and Egg Cholesterol of Layers

Group	Serum cholesterol (mg/dl)		Egg cholesterol (mg/gm yolk)		
	Pre treatment (Day 0)	Post treatment (Day 84)	Pre treatment (Day 0)	Post treatment (Day 84)	Percent Reduction
T ₁	160.5 ^a ±1.55	160.4 ^a ±1.57	18.3 ^a ±0.65	18.0 ^a ±0.12	-
T ₂	159.1 ^a ±1.40	151.7 ^b ±1.77	17.9 ^a ±0.64	16.3 ^b ±0.26	8.94
T ₃	158.6 ^a ±1.96	152.8 ^b ±2.17	18.2 ^a ±0.53	16.8 ^b ±0.29	7.69
T ₄	160.6 ^a ±1.45	151.2 ^b ±1.81	18.1 ^a ±0.50	16.2 ^b ±0.21	10.50

- Values are Mean±SE
- Values in columns with different superscripts differ significantly (p<0.05)

The cDNA samples prepared by Reverse Transcriptase PCR (RT-PCR) were tested by *in vitro* amplification of 543 bp fragment of GAPDH gene (housekeeping/ endogenous control/ reference gene) for purity and integrity (Plate 01). The SREBP-2 and LDL gene amplification conditions were standardized by simple PCR. The gene specific primer set was used to amplify 339 bp fragment of SREBP-2 gene (Plate 02) and 108 bp fragment of LDL gene (Plate 03) using representative cDNA samples.

The mRNA expression levels of SREBP-2 on day 84, in liver and ovarian follicle samples of Jabalpur colour birds supplemented with indigenous herbs *N. sativa* and *W. somnifera* have been presented in terms of fold change in expression of SREBP-2 (Table 03).

Table 03: mRNA Expression of SREBP-2 Gene in Liver and Ovary of Layers

Tissues	T ₁		T ₂		T ₃		T ₄	
	Δ Ct	2 ^{-ΔΔCt}						
Liver	3.9 ^A ±0.04	1	1.9 ^C ±0.04	4.1	2.5 ^B ±0.04	2.7	1.8 ^C ±0.04	4.2
Ovary	5.1 ^A ±0.03	1	2.2 ^C ±0.03	7.1	2.7 ^B ±0.03	5.3	2.0 ^D ±0.03	8.5

- Means bearing different superscripts within same row differ significantly (p<0.05)

T₁- Control

T₂- *N.sativa* (20 gm/kg feed)

T₃- *W. somnifera*
(20 gm/kg feed)

T₄- *N.sativa* (10 gm/kg feed)
+ *W. somnifera* (10 gm/kg feed)

The mRNA expression level of SREBP-2 gene in liver and ovarian follicle samples of layers was significantly ($p < 0.05$) up-regulated in all treatment groups as compared to control group. In liver samples maximum up- regulation was found in group T₄ (4.2 fold) supplemented with *N. sativa* and *W. Somnifera* (10 gm/kg feed each), followed by group T₂ (4.1 fold) supplemented with *N. sativa* alone (20 gm/kg feed). However, in group T₃ (*W. somnifera*, 20 gm/kg feed) minimum up-regulation (2.7 fold) was observed relative to control group. In ovarian follicle samples maximum up- regulation was found in group T₄ (8.5 fold) supplemented with *N. sativa* and *W. somnifera* followed by group T₂ (7.1 fold) supplemented with *N. sativa* alone and group T₃ (5.3 fold) supplemented with *W. somnifera* alone.

The mRNA expression levels of LDLr on day 84, in liver and ovarian follicle samples of layers supplemented with indigenous herbs *N. sativa* and *W. somnifera* have been presented in terms of fold change in expression of LDLr (Table 03).

The mRNA expression level of LDLr gene in liver and ovarian follicle samples of layers was significantly ($p < 0.05$) up-regulated in all treatment groups as compared to control group. In liver samples maximum up- regulation (5.2 fold) was found in group T₄ supplemented with *N. sativa* and *W. somnifera* (10 gm/kg feed each), followed by group T₂ (4.9 fold) supplemented with *N. sativa* alone (20 gm/kg feed). However, in group T₃ (*W. somnifera*, 20 gm/kg feed) minimum up-regulation (3.0 fold) was observed relative to control group. In ovarian follicle samples maximum up- regulation was found in group T₄ (8.7 fold) supplemented with *N. sativa* and *W. Somnifera* followed by group T₂ (7.9 fold) supplemented with *N. sativa* alone and group T₃ (5.9 fold) supplemented with *W. somnifera* alone.

Table 04: mRNA Expression of LDLr Gene in Liver and Ovary of Layers

Tissues	T ₁		T ₂		T ₃		T ₄	
	Δ Ct	2 ^{-ΔΔCt}						
Liver	3.5 ^A ± 0.04	1	1.2 ^C ± 0.04	4.9	1.9 ^B ± 0.04	3.0	1.1 ^C ± 0.04	5.2
Ovary	4.9 ^A ± 0.04	1	1.9 ^C ± 0.04	7.9	2.3 ^B ± 0.04	5.9	1.7 ^D ± 0.04	8.7

- Means bearing different superscripts within same row differ significantly ($p < 0.05$)

T₁- Control

T₂- *N.sativa* (20 gm/kg feed)

T₃- *W. somnifera*
(20 gm/kg feed)

T₄- *N.sativa* (10 gm/kg feed)
+ *W. somnifera* (10 gm/kg feed)

Discussion

Cholesterol balance in egg-laying fowl varies significantly from that in omnivorous mammals. Laying hens usually meet their bodies needs for cholesterol entirely by de novo synthesis, which occurs primarily in the liver and ovary. Cholesterol, after being synthesized in liver is incorporated into vitellogenin (VTG) and triglyceride-rich very low density lipoprotein (VLDL) particles, which are then secreted into the bloodstream and subsequently taken up by growing oocytes via receptor-mediated endocytosis. VLDL and VTG are then intracellularly transformed into yolk, constituting approximately 60 and 24 per cent of yolk dry matter and about 95 and 5 per cent of yolk cholesterol, respectively. Thus, cholesterol is primarily expelled through the egg in hen. In laying hens, liver and ovary are the primary sites of cholesterol biosynthesis. Thus, the mRNA expression profile of SREBP-2 and LDLr was studied in liver and ovarian follicles of birds.

The regulation of cholesterol synthesis and uptake from plasma is dependent on coordinated changes in the level of mRNAs of key genes that are known to regulate cholesterol synthesis and cholesterol uptake. Lipid homeostasis in vertebrate cells is controlled by sterol regulatory element-binding proteins (SREBPs). SREBPs directly trigger the expression of over 30 genes involved in the synthesis and uptake of cholesterol, fatty acids, triglycerides and phospholipids. The soluble form of SREBP-2, enters the nucleus where it activates transcription by binding to 10-bp sterol regulatory elements (SREs) in the enhancer regions of target genes, i.e., HMGs, HMGR and LDLr. When cells are overloaded with sterols, SREBP-2 remains bound to endoplasmic reticulum membranes and consequently transcription of the target genes declines. The LDL receptor provides cholesterol to cells by binding and internalizing LDL. When cholesterol demands are high, the LDL receptor gene is transcribed actively and consequently more LDL is internalized. However, when cholesterol accumulates within the cell, transcription of this gene is repressed causing a decrease in LDL internalization.

Camphene, a monoterpene, exerts its hypolipidemic action by affecting SREBP-1 and MTP Expression. Camphene activates the expression of SREBP1 transcription factor while does not substantially alter SREBP-2, indicating that camphene regulates primarily genes involved in fatty acid rather than in cholesterol biosynthesis. However, in present study the indigenous plants increased SREBP-2 expression thus affect cholesterol homeostasis and biosynthesis. Increased expression of SREBP-2 possibly suggests that reduction of cholesterol by indigenous plants, results in a SREBP-2 dependent increase in LDLr expression and scavenging of circulating LDL cholesterol. Treatment with *N. sativa* and *W. somnifera* led to the activation of SREBP-2 which targets and activates LDL receptor, thereby facilitating plasma cholesterol efflux into the cell to maintain cholesterol homeostasis.

In the present study, a significant increase in mRNA expression levels of SREBP-2 and LDLr was observed in both liver and ovarian follicles of birds which were supplemented with *Nigella sativa* and *Withania Somnifera*. Thus, findings of present experiment suggest that the SREBP-2 and LDLr in liver and ovarian follicles of birds responds to serum and egg cholesterol levels which were significantly reduced by indigenous herbs.

Further, the mRNA expression of SREBP-2 and LDLr was up-regulated more in ovarian follicles as compared to liver. Washburn & Nix described that if the blood cholesterol reservoir reaches a certain threshold, then it is dumped in the egg and it is expected as a positive correlation after the level of blood cholesterol was sufficient to fill the reservoir. On the other hand, if the egg is not a dumping reservoir for excess blood cholesterol, but a certain proportion of the blood cholesterol is shunted into the egg regardless of the level of reservoir then a negative correlation might be expected to exist. There is a very real possibility that within the same hen both situations may be operating at different times depending on the level of production, position in clutch cycle, dietary levels of cholesterol and other factors. In the present investigation, the mRNA expression levels of SREBP-2 and LDLr genes up-regulated more in ovarian follicles indicating more reduction of cholesterol in egg yolk than serum, which seems to be a positive correlation between yolk and serum cholesterol. Similarly, yolk cholesterol level did not always parallel to serum cholesterol level when different types of dietary fats were supplemented in the diet of layers.

Supplementation of 0.1 per cent pravastatin (hypocholesterolemic drug) in the diets of chickens decreased plasma LDL-cholesterol concentrations and increased the levels of nuclear forms of SREBP-2 and increased gene expression of 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl CoA reductase (HMGR) and low-density lipoprotein receptor (LDLr) in liver, relative to a control group. In contrast, feeding of 3 per cent cholesterol-supplemented diet increased plasma total- and LDL-cholesterol concentrations but decreased levels of nuclear forms of SREBP-2 and reduced gene expression of HMGR and LDLr. These findings are in accordance with the findings of the present study.

Conclusion

The poultry industry has continued to seek to reduce egg cholesterol concentrations so that an egg with reduced cholesterol will be available to those consumers who need to lower their dietary cholesterol intake. In the present study, dietary supplementation of *Nigella sativa* and *Withania Somnifera* significantly reduced the levels of cholesterol in serum and egg of layers. Further, a significant increase in the mRNA expression levels of Sterol Regulatory Element Binding Protein-2 (SREBP-2) and Low-Density Lipoprotein receptor (LDLr) gene in liver and ovarian follicles of birds was also observed indicating the role of these two genes in hypocholesterolemic activity of indigenous herbs.

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Conflict of Interest

Authors declares no conflict of interest.

Author's Contribution

Conceptualization: VG; Funding acquisition: RKS; Experimental Work: VG; Sample analysis: VG, SJ, AS; Roles/Writing - original draft: VG, SJ, VKG; Writing - review & editing: RKS, AS, VKG.

Plate 01: Agarose gel electrophoresis confirming amplification of GAPDH gene (543 bp) of Jabalpur colour bird
Lane M : 100 bp ladder
Lane 1-16 : Gene specific amplified product
Lane N : No template (negative) control

Plate 02: Agarose gel electrophoresis confirming amplification of SREBP-2 gene (339 bp) of Jabalpur colour bird
Lane M : 100 bp ladder
Lane 1-16 : Gene specific amplified product
Lane N : No template (negative) control

Plate 03: Agarose gel electrophoresis confirming amplification of LDLr gene (108 bp) of Jabalpur colour bird
Lane M : 100 bp ladder
Lane 1-16 : Gene specific amplified product
Lane N : No template (negative) control

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